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Insight into the Understanding of Consciousness in Bantu Cosmology

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Abstract

This paper presents an understanding of consciousness based on Bantu cosmology. The author's motivation is to discuss consciousness in a new light. The writer has included some stories that he heard and events he witnessed during his childhood. In Bantu cosmology, the universe is governed by souls or spirits (taken here as consciousness). These are found in all elements of the universe: in trees, stones, wind, animals, and human beings, etc. The author argues that this idea is worth investigating to assess whether the Bantu understanding of consciousness can provide a better understanding of physical theories concerning consciousness.

1. Introduction

Africans stress the fundamental view that two different personalities characterize each individual and everything else in the universe, such as a human being (the physical body) and consciousness. The latter exercises a powerful influence on the body. The belief that consciousness is imbued in everything in the universe (for instance, seed or plant) has led them

to argue that although plants do not have a brain or a nervous system, the consciousness or soul inside the seed gives instructions for all aspects of its life. Therefore, plants show environmental awareness and follow the sun's path from east to west. The intelligent software (consciousness) tells the roots that they need to go downwards under the influence of gravity and tells the branches to grow outwards or against gravity. The consciousness is the fundamental unit giving instructions such as dividing, producing and reproducing.

This paper proposes that consciousness is fundamental and suggests a new framework that can take us beyond the current understanding of matter, energy, time, and space. The motivation for this article is introduced, followed by a discussion describing the ideas and concepts of consciousness in Bantu cosmology. The paper study finishes up with suggestions for additional work. This paper outlines how consciousness is embedded in matter and can be explained as a physical process.

2. Consciousness in Bantu Cosmology

2.1 Consciousness as a Force

This idea of consciousness is powerfully expressed by the Bantu¹ when somebody dies. They usually use the expression: “He or she is gone!” Gone where? A detailed discussion about life and death can be found in Anganga (2011). They acknowledge that the thing that is gone away is the spirit, soul or consciousness, the real person (the I). Thus, the body is just the object of the thing that is gone. Consciousness is the force giving life to a body. Therefore, the Bantu consider plants and trees sacred and give them a unique and holy status. They believe in an unbreakable link between human beings, plants, and trees. Whenever they enter a forest, they feel like they are among their kin, brothers, and sisters.

They feel close to nature and stress that human beings, trees and forests have a common origin, which is a divine one. They argue that trees and plants are living entities imbued with consciousness and sacred beings. In several parts of Africa, before cutting down a tree for any reason, one must perform a rite or say certain words to appease the tree since cutting it down

¹ Bantu people are the speakers of Bantu languages and are found in sub-Saharan Africa.

kills it. Sometimes, before cutting down a tree, a special request is made to the soul residing inside the plant to leave and move somewhere else so that the tree can be felled.

This view shows beyond any doubt that the Bantu feel that there is a unity between animals, plants and stones and that they think themselves to be in communion with these entities. Thus, these people have greater respect for all living entities. Generally, in Bantu society, people are afraid of destroying or cutting an old tree, as they believe it is the home of a great or old soul. Trees are not typically cut down unless exceptional circumstances dictate that the family or clan should do so, for instance, when trees used as medicines that are needed to cure certain diseases.

This respect or adoration for nature and its elements is due to many factors. The Bantu feel that they have a close relationship with nature (trees, animals, etc.) and that this can help them live in a more peaceful, less complicated way than nomads, for instance. The Bantu get their clothes, food, medicines, instruments and weapons from a tree or the forest. They argue that all-natural kingdoms are precious for life and are indispensable, and thus always seek communion (intimacy) with them.

2.2 The Soul or Spirit Has a Subtle Body

I was also fascinated to learn about masks or statues in understanding consciousness in Bantu culture. The Luba² of the Kasai province in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) claim that they know where a spirit lives and can use it as an object and place it within a mask so that the mask is alive, animated and able to respond to instructions. Does this mechanism exist? The Luba³ argue that a tool like teleportation or a quantum hologram can transfer information. One of the ways in which we can gain insight into teleportation is through the

² The Luba people are an ethno-linguistic group indigenous to the south-central region of the DRC.

³ Is it possible to transfer consciousness from one body to another? The Luba claim that they know this process and claim that they can order or instruct a soul living in a plant to move to another place. It is common knowledge that in Bantu cosmology, it is possible to move the soul or consciousness of a living human being to an animal, a tree, or a bird, and vice versa. I personally heard many people talking about this as I was growing up in the Congo. For instance, there was an instance where a man transferred his consciousness to a particular animal, but unfortunately when the animal was killed, the man died shortly afterwards, as his soul (consciousness) could not return to his human body.

work of Chary (2018). What mechanisms are there to move consciousness from a living entity to a non-living one?

The Bantu do not believe that there is anything in the universe without a soul or spirit: they look at matter itself as a form of spirit or soul because the soul uses it whenever it wants to. It appears that the Bantu do not consider the soul or spirit as a spiritual or immaterial substance, as a Western person might. For them, the soul or spirit has a subtle body capable of infinite transformation, moving or traveling instantaneously from one place to another, and can become visible or invisible at will. It can also move from one body to another without restrictions as if there were no obstacle.

These people take great care to protect consciousness, the 'I' that makes up the individuality, i.e., the body. In addition, what is inside the body and what goes out of the body, such as secretions or excretions like hair, sperm, blood, and urine, must be protected because these represent the life of the 'I', and can be used to destroy the 'I'. These elements and the 'I' appear to be the same thing because consciousness is equally distributed throughout all body parts. Similarly, the name given to a person is not just etiquette but forms the person's personality and has fundamental importance.

Therefore, death is not seen as the destruction of the physical body, but as a necessary passage or bridge between material and spiritual life. A spiritual body continues to exist: life does not end with death but goes beyond it, and the soul continues to live, transcends death, and continues into the afterlife. For the Bantu, death is not the end of the world but is the continuity of life in another dimension or universe. This vision of the universe teaches us the victory of life over death. Africa has something to offer in the search for an understanding of consciousness, and my belief is that this contribution will be outstanding in this debate.

2.3 Sacred Masks

The African continent is home to various cultures, each unique, differing from the others in terms of its languages, traditions, science, technology, and artistic forms. For instance, figurines and masks have a profound meaning and reflect the richness of a people's history, myths, science, etc. These objects' deep significance and importance in cosmology cannot be

overestimated. For instance, masks and statuettes are believed to be inhabited by the spirits of ancestors or geniuses. African art is often approached with negativity, ignorance, prejudice, and preconceived, mostly false ideas. Many essential points should be made so that readers and researchers understand that these items are not:

- Theatrical accessories.
- Objects of decorative art.
- Artistic objects conditioned by European or Western tastes.
- Inert objects.
- Witchcraft objects.

Although there are many types of masks, some of them are sacred, as these represent ancestors, deities, or forces. These sacred beings use a statue or mask to appear and express themselves, meaning that the cover or statuette is alive. Furthermore, these masks represent the wisdom and mystery of the supernatural forces that animate them. Apart from the sacred masks, other widely-known types of masks are:

- Warrior masks: These are used for the conquest and defense of territory.
- Griots wear griot masks as spy masks; they listen, observe, and relate to the sacred masks.
- Singers masks: Genealogists use these to sing the praises of people.
- Dancers mask: These are worn by dance virtuosos, who have a strong vitality.
- Beggars mask: Beggars are both at the bottom and the top of the hierarchy and go from house to house begging for food.

2.4 Wholeness

In this cosmology, no single element of the universe is independent of the others. Everything is linked or interlinked, and this interdependence is vital for survival. The vibrations outside us are not separate from us but are constantly interacting with us, and there is a penetration of both the visible and the invisible universe. The universe appears to Bantu people as beings like themselves, who affect each other. This idea is similar to the holographic universe hypothesis, first proposed by Bohm (1981). The universe and life are conceived as a unity where everything is connected, constantly interacting. The visible and the invisible are linked.

Bantu cosmology has a philosophical view of consciousness. The universe appears to Bantu people as beings like themselves, who affect each other. The universe and life are conceived as a unity where everything is connected and constantly interacting. We must start to see the whole picture, embrace this spirit of wholeness, and understand that we are all inextricably linked through our consciousness. Our understanding of consciousness through the cosmology of the Bantu is embodied by the Zulu personal declaration,⁴ shown in Table 1-1:

Table 1-1: The Zulu personal declaration

The Zulu Personal Declaration
I;
I am;
I am alive;
I am conscious and aware;
I am unique;
I am who I say I am; I am the UQOBO (essence).
I forever evolve inwardly and outwardly in response to the challenge of my nature;
I am the face of humanity.
The face of humanity is my face.
I contemplate myself and see everything in me.
I perceive; that which I sense is form.
The form is an enduring value.
Value is eternal consciousness;
Consciousness is that in which all things have their origin;
It does not change; it exists from eternity to eternity;
It is an infinite cluster of clusters of itself;
It is forever evolving in response to the challenge of its nature.
It is ultimate value;
It is UQOBO.
The value metamorphoses into a phenomenon;
Each phenomenon is a total of smaller forms.
Phenomena form clusters to produce other phenomena.

⁴ Asante, M.K. 2015. "Zulu culture." Accessed December 08, 2018. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L3cW9xl_k2A

I am phenomena; I am a person.
I am UQOBO; I am the consciousness.
The infinity is a unity; it cannot be destroyed;
I am a constituent of the unity;
I cannot be destroyed;
The infinity and I are inseparable;
I cannot exist outside of the infinity,
For there is no outside of it.
Everything is inside the infinity;
UQOBO is the infinity.
It is a whole.

2.5 Conclusion

Consciousness appears to be universal, and every living and non-living entity has some degree of consciousness. For a Bantu, consciousness seems to be the source of everything and is the concept that explains everything. If we accept this new view of consciousness, profound changes in the universe, ranging from social and spiritual to physical, can occur. A theory of consciousness will arise as a result and lead to a leap forward in our understanding of the universe and ourselves, based on a better framework. In the same way, as for thermodynamics or classical mechanics, a proposal detailing the laws of consciousness is then just a matter of time.

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